

INTEGRATION AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF A MODERN TEACHER

Tatyana Markovna Gozman

Director of the state budgetary institution of the Kaliningrad region professional educational organization "Pedagogical College", candidate of pedagogical sciences, associate professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10391778>

Abstract. *The acmeological development of a teacher means his holistic professional development as a specialist, an individual and a spiritually mature person, this is self-improvement, self-development, both in professional, personal, and spiritual aspects, the growth of self-awareness, reflection on pedagogical activity and professional behavior of the teacher as a subject of professional activity [3]. In the concept of acmeology, the qualities of a teacher are considered as conditions for the quality of education.*

Keywords: *integration in education, formation, upbringing, powerful pedagogical potential, education, training.*

Integration in education is considered as a complex process that appears in various variants, types, types, forms and is one of the means of ensuring holistic knowledge of the world and a person's ability to think systematically when solving practical problems.

In this context, integration is actively considered in the concept of a competency-based approach to education. S.E. Shishov and I.G. Agapov note the importance of integration as the highest level of interaction, characterized by the success and creative activity of a person in transforming (developing) society in accordance with universal human values.

In modern education, from the standpoint of student-oriented pedagogy, the creation of an integrative environment for all participants in the educational process is relevant today (V. G. Vorontsova, V. A. Kozyrev).

Based on the opinion of researchers that the educational process is a system, a process of interaction between its subjects, which involves mutual change of all participants in the educational process (T. M. Davydenko, T. I. Shamova), it is necessary to take into account the features of the professional and personal development of a teacher in an integrative environment.

The didactic structure of the educational process, according to the authors, represents the interrelation of such components as subjects of the educational process, target, stimulating-motivational, content, operational-activity, control-regulatory and reflective.

Consequently, in the educational process the teacher acts as both a participant and an organizer of integration processes.

Most researchers (I.A. Kolesnikova, D.G. Levites, V.V. Serikov and others) note that pedagogical activity is characterized by a certain logic of the process, namely: goals, objectives, dominant content; the nature of the relationship, the choice of methodological (technological) support, criteria for evaluating the result.

This logic is ensured by the meanings of the subject of pedagogical activity, which contain powerful pedagogical potential, pointing to the need for a systemic and holistic self-awareness, to the possibility of individual knowledge of the surrounding world in its entirety. "Discovering the true meaning that is embedded in a particular pedagogical concept (situation, activity), and

mastering the logic of its implementation is necessary to acquire such an important property as subjectivity.

Lack of awareness of meaning at the individual level gives rise to spontaneity (at best, algorithmic) of professional behavior, turning the teacher into a tool that can be easily manipulated from the outside” [2, p. 219]. The teacher’s awareness of the meaning of pedagogical activity determines the teacher’s independent professional thinking, awareness of himself as a subject of a personal development situation, he reflects himself in the role of a specific bearer of personal experience, offers this experience to the student as a means of supporting and solving his life problems [4].

A teacher’s author’s pedagogical system is defined as a systemic quality “generated by a specific embodiment of the logic of “knowledge about a skill” or knowledge about the logic of working with an “object” in pedagogical activity” [2]. Thus, this system can be characterized from the standpoint of technology as a logical sequence of operations reflected at the level of professional consciousness, reflecting an objective, most harmonized in relation to certain conditions, reproducible way to achieve a specific goal (pedagogical) [2].

A.A. Derkach and N.V. Kuzmin note that the main system-forming factor of a person’s professionalism is the image of the desired result that the subject of the activity strives for. The need to achieve it, analysis of measures of progress towards it, the search for reasons that facilitate and hinder its achievement form the professionalism of the individual [1].

A scientific field that deals with the study of creative periods in a person’s life, stages of maturity, accompanied by an increase in the efficiency of professional activity, the professionalism of mature people, the patterns of mental development of the individual during the heyday (acme) and the multi-vertex process of ascension to professionalism (B.G. Ananyev, A.A. Derkach, N.V. Kuzmina, A.N. Rybnikov, etc.).

Acmeology distinguishes the following categories: creative individuality, the process of self-development and self-improvement, creative experience as a result of self-actualization. Slastenin V.A. And L.S. Podymova note that these categories constitute the basic foundations of innovative pedagogy [5].

It is characteristic that a collective subject participates in the organization of pedagogical processes, and, of course, ethical rules are a kind of mechanism for preserving the integrity of this subject [2]. An organized integrative educational environment “contains powerful pedagogical potential, pointing to the need for systemic and holistic self-awareness, the possibility of individual knowledge of the world around us in its entirety.

A person’s awareness and experience of partiality, i.e. insufficiency, individual imperfection also has a deep pedagogical meaning, on the one hand, giving an incentive and guidance on the path of (self) improvement, on the other, awakening a sense of belonging, responsibility for the quality of the whole of which you are a part” [2, p. 114]. Integration is focused on “the holistic and sustainable development of educational systems and subjects of the educational process in conditions of creative activity” [3, p. 7].

The teacher and the students, being in creative interaction and cooperation, ensure success for each other in their self-realization, in the development of the spiritual and value potential of the individual. Such integration makes it possible to create conditions for the development of the acmeological position of the teacher as a professional orientation towards success in his own teaching activities, in the work of the entire school staff, in the training and education of each

student, in the development of his creative potential, and an attitude towards self-development [3, p. 8].

The acmeological development of a teacher means his holistic professional development as a specialist, an individual and a spiritually mature person, this is self-improvement, self-development, both in professional, personal, and spiritual aspects, the growth of self-awareness, reflection on pedagogical activity and professional behavior of the teacher as a subject of professional activity [3]. In the concept of acmeology, the qualities of a teacher are considered as conditions for the quality of education.

The acmeological position of a teacher is characterized by such qualities of a specialist as: “openness to mastering new things; a systematic way of thinking when developing optimal models of professional activity; the ability to objectively self-assess one’s professional behavior; high motivation for achievements in work, etc.” [3, p. 9]. Thus, in our opinion, the acmeological position is determined by a person’s ability to be a facilitator - helping students in self-knowledge, self-determination, self-realization (Sergeev I.S.). Consequently, the acmeological position, in our opinion, integrates such subject positions as: learner, self-organizing, teaching.

It is necessary to take into account that the teacher is an adult who has direct experience of teaching activities, and objective or subjective difficulties in its implementation. Based on the understanding of the subject as a bearer of objective-practical activity and cognition, effecting changes in other people and in oneself, and a person’s subjectivity is manifested in his life activity, communication, self-awareness, subjectivity is determined by a person’s ability to be a strategist of activity, to set and adjust goals, to be aware of motives, independently build actions and evaluate their compliance with plans, build life plans (G.M. Kodzhaspirova, A.Yu. Kodzhaspirov). It should be noted that in reality, the teacher performs various types of subjective activity, namely: cognizes (masters) pedagogical reality, its development in the modern educational space - the subject being taught; creates, develops a personal product of his pedagogical activity. It should be noted that in reality, the teacher performs various types of subjective activity, namely: cognizes (masters) pedagogical reality, its development in the modern educational space - the subject being taught; creates and develops a personal product of his teaching activities, perspective-oriented – a self-organizing subject; implements previous types of subject activity in his daily teaching practice - the teaching subject. Of great importance in the development of a teacher’s professional activity is the integration of these subject positions, as a synthesis, fusion, formation

REFERENCES

1. Derkach A.A., Kuzmina N.V. Acmeology: ways to achieve the heights of professionalism. // Socio-political processes, organization and management (economics). – M., 1991.
2. Kolesnikova I.A. Pedagogical reality: experience of interparadigm reflection. Course of lectures on the philosophy of pedagogy - St. Petersburg: “Childhood-Press”, 2001. – 288 p.
3. Maksimova V.N. Acmeology: new quality of education. // Head teacher – 2004 – No. 3. – P. 3-23.
4. Serikov V.V. Education and personality. Theory and practice of designing pedagogical systems. – M.: Publishing Corporation “Logos”, 1999. – 272 p.
5. Slastenin V.A., Podymova L.S. Pedagogy: Innovative activities. – M.: IChP “Magister Publishing House”, 1997. – 224 p.